

Kinetics of Thermal Decomposition of Limestone

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Decomposition kinetics of limestone were studied in the interval of 650–950° in air and under vacuum by thermogravimetric method. The decomposition followed the kinetics based on diffusion of products away from the interface coupled with chemical reaction.

THE kinetics of thermal decomposition of limestone have been widely studied. Furnas¹ stated that calcination of limestone proceeds only from the outside of the piece inwards over a very narrow zone, practically a line. Maskill and Turner² showed the importance of the rate of diffusion away of CO₂ on the rate of decomposition of calcite at constant temperature in air. Britton *et al.*³ described the decomposition of calcite as being a surface reaction and have not considered diffusion as a rate controlling step.

In the present investigation, the kinetics of thermal decomposition of limestone have been studied with respect to variation in impurities and atmospheric pressure.

Experimental

The samples of limestone selected for study were analysed by following standard chemical procedure⁴. Limestone cubes (≈1 cm edge) were prepared from cut samples which were ground with emery powder (below 110 mesh) and polished with Cr₂O₃ powder to have polished surfaces. Surface area, volume and density of the cubes were determined.

Samples were held in a small platinum crucible and suspended by platinum wire from a thermobalance and introduced inside the uniform temperature zone of a tubular thermogravimetric furnace preheated to the experimental temperature (± 5°). The weight loss was recorded by the thermobalance at suitable time intervals. An arrangement was made to pass purified and dried CO₂ gas through the furnace to prevent early decomposition of sample. Some experiments were carried out under vacuum (2–3 mm Hg) for which certain alterations in the above set up were carried out.

Results and Discussion

Density and composition of the samples are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DENSITY AND COMPOSITION OF SAMPLES

	Limestone (L ₁)	Limestone (L ₂)
Source	Jhinkpani	Cuddapah
Density (gm ⁻³)	2.717	2.704
Loss on ignition (wt %)	38.01	36.05
SiO ₂ (wt %)	10.65	23.90
Al ₂ O ₃ (wt %)	2.66	0.13
Fe ₂ O ₃ (wt %)	0.55	0.11
CaO (wt %)	47.06	23.70
MgO (wt %)	0.64	15.95
Total	99.57	99.84

It was felt that some modification of the equation $(W/W_0)^{1/3} = 1 - K't$ was necessary to explain the discrepancy observed by Britton *et al.*³ and others. It was considered that since it is a reversible reaction, the possibility of back-reaction can not be overlooked and further, the equation $(W/W_0)^{1/3} = 1 - K't$ which gives a measure of the forward reaction (CaCO₃ → CaO + CO₂), needs modification. Considering the above factor, the following equation was developed,

$$\alpha = - (K_1 - K_2 P_0) \frac{K_2 d}{K_3} + (K_1 - K_2 P_0)$$

where, P₀ = pressure of CO₂ at the crystal surface at a temperature *t*, *d* = depth of calcination from the crystal surface, α = rate of weight loss per unit area *i.e.* overall rate of decomposition of calcium carbonate per unit area of decomposing surface, K₁ = rate of forward reaction per unit area which may be taken as constant, K₂ = rate constant of backward reaction per unit area, and K₃ = diffusion coefficient of CO₂ through the decomposed CaO layer.

By the law of mass action,

Overall rate of reaction = (Rate of forward reaction) – (Rate of backward reaction)

$$= (K_1 - K_2 P) \quad (1)$$

where, K₂P is the rate of backward reaction, P being the pressure of CO₂ at the decomposing

interface (under equilibrium condition, P is equal to the dissociation pressure). Now the amount of CO_2 formed at the interface should be equal to that diffusing through the decomposed CaO . Assuming that the rate of diffusion is inversely proportional to thickness, the following equation can be written,

$$\alpha = K_2 (P - P_0)/d$$

$$\text{or } P = \frac{\alpha d}{K_2} + P_0 \quad (2)$$

Substituting the value of P in equation (1),

$$\alpha = K_1 - K_2 \left(\frac{\alpha d}{K_2} + P_0 \right) = K_1 - K_2 \frac{\alpha d}{K_2} - K_2 P_0 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{or } \alpha = (K_1 - K_2 P_0) (1 + K_2 d/K_2)^{-1} \\ = (K_1 - K_2 P_0) (1 - K_2 d/K_2)$$

Neglecting the higher powers of $K_2 d/K_2$ on the assumption that $K_2 d/K_2$ is a small fraction of 1.

Equation (3) shows that since α is a positive quantity, $K_2 d/K_2$ is less than 1. If the assumption is made that the overall reaction rate α is not much different from the rate of the forward reaction (K_1), then $K_2 d/K_2$ will be a small fraction of 1. Further when the overall reaction rate differs considerably from the rate of forward reaction, the value of $K_2 P_0$ becomes high (P_0 increase with P (equation 2) and P determines the rate of backward reaction) and $K_2 d/K_2$ remains small fraction of 1.

$$\text{or } \alpha = -(K_1 - K_2 P_0) \cdot \frac{K_2 d}{K_2} + (K_1 - K_2 P_0) \quad (4)$$

According to equation (4), a plot of α vs d should be a straight line, the slope and intercept of which will give the values of $(K_1 - K_2 P_0)K_2/K_2$ and $(K_1 - K_2 P_0)$, respectively.

Under vacuum, pressure P_0 on the crystal surface may be taken as equal to zero and equation (4) is then reduced to

$$\alpha = -K_1 K_2 d/K_2 + K_1$$

As before, plots of α against d should give straight line, the slope of which will be equal to $K_1 \cdot K_2/K_2$ and the intercept equal to K_1 .

From the slope of the weight loss vs time curves, total weight loss per minute at a particular depth (d) may be calculated. Surface area may be calculated at a particular d (Fig. 1). Now rate of weight loss per unit area in $\text{g min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ may be obtained at various depths of calcination.

Fig. 1. Section of a partially decomposed limestone cube.

The values of K_1 for various limestone cubes heated under vacuum at different temperatures are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF K_1 FOR VARIOUS LIMESTONE CUBES HEATED UNDER VACUUM AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Sample no.	Temp. °C	K_1 $\text{g min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$
L ₁	650	1.95×10^{-4}
L ₅	650	2.02×10^{-4}
L ₁	750	2.48×10^{-3}
L ₅	750	8.1×10^{-4}
L ₁	850	1.39×10^{-2}
L ₅	850	5.0×10^{-3}
L ₁	950	2.68×10^{-4}
L ₅	950	12.05×10^{-3}

Values of K_1 i.e. the rate of the forward reaction of the decomposition of limestone as given in Table 2, were utilised to calculate the values of energy of activation by the Arrhenius equation. Values of $\log_{10} K_1$ were plotted against $1/T$ (Table 3) and from the slope, the values of energy of activation were calculated (Fig. 2).

TABLE 3—VALUES OF $\log_{10} K_1$ AND $1/T$ FOR LIMESTONE CUBES

Temp. °C	K_1 ($\text{g min}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$)		$\log_{10} K_1$		$1/T$
	L ₁	L ₅	L ₁	L ₅	
650	1.95×10^{-4}	2.02×10^{-4}	-3.71	-3.69	1.08×10^{-3}
750	2.48×10^{-3}	8.1×10^{-4}	-2.60	-3.69	0.97×10^{-3}
850	1.39×10^{-2}	5.8×10^{-3}	-1.85	-2.23	0.89×10^{-3}
950	2.68×10^{-2}	12.05×10^{-3}	-1.57	-1.91	0.82×10^{-3}

The values of K_1 were found to be 35.69 and 26.74 kcal/100 g for samples L₁ and L₅, respectively. These values were much lower than the

Fig. 2. Effect of temperature on the rate of decomposition of limestone.

values of the energy of decomposition of calcium carbonate which is 40 kcal/100 g. This is possibly due to the fact that impurities present in these samples, such as SiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 react at these temperatures with calcium carbonate forming $\text{CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, $2\text{CaO} \cdot \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ and $2\text{CaO} \cdot \text{SiO}_2$, and the rate of the reaction ($\text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$) is lower than the rate of the following reactions,

Moreover, products formed during the decomposition of limestone, which consists not only calcium carbonate but also MgCO_3 , SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 , consist of CaO as well as silicate, aluminate, ferrites of calcium and magnesium oxide. The overall heat of reaction per 100 g is much lower than the heat of decomposition of calcium carbonate, as the heat of decomposition of pure MgCO_3 is 27 kcal/84 g and the formation of calcium silicates, calcium aluminates, calcium ferrites from CaO are attended with evolution of heat.

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